

On the mean value of the Smarandache LCM function

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Abstract For any positive integer n , the F.Smarandache LCM function $SL(n)$ is defined as the smallest positive integer k such that $n \mid [1, 2, \dots, k]$, where $[1, 2, \dots, k]$ denotes the least common multiple of $1, 2, \dots, k$, and let $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_s^{\alpha_s}$ be the factorization of n into prime powers, then $\bar{\Omega}(n) = \alpha_1 p_1 + \alpha_2 p_2 + \dots + \alpha_s p_s$. The main purpose of this paper is using the elementary methods to study the mean value properties of $\bar{\Omega}(n)SL(n)$, and give a sharper asymptotic formula for it.

Keywords F.Smarandache LCM function, $\bar{\Omega}(n)$ function, mean value, asymptotic formula.

§1. Introduction and Results

For any positive integer n , the famous F.Smarandache LCM function $SL(n)$ defined as the smallest positive integer k such that $n \mid [1, 2, \dots, k]$, where $[1, 2, \dots, k]$ denotes the least common multiple of $1, 2, \dots, k$. For example, the first few values of $SL(n)$ are $SL(1) = 1, SL(2) = 2, SL(3) = 3, SL(4) = 4, SL(5) = 5, SL(6) = 3, SL(7) = 7, SL(8) = 4, SL(9) = 6, SL(10) = 5, SL(11) = 11, SL(12) = 4, SL(13) = 13, SL(14) = 7, SL(15) = 5, \dots$. About the elementary properties of $SL(n)$, some authors had studied it, and obtained some interesting results, see reference [2] and [3]. For example, Lv Zhongtian [4] studied the mean value properties of $SL(n)$, and proved that for any fixed positive integer k and any real number $x > 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} SL(n) = \frac{\pi^2}{12} \cdot \frac{x^2}{\ln x} + \sum_{i=2}^k \frac{b_i \cdot x^2}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),$$

where b_i ($i = 2, 3, \dots, k$) are computable constants.

On the other hand, Chen Jianbin [5] studied the value distribution properties of $SL(n)$, and proved that for any real number $x > 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} (SL(n) - P(n))^2 = \frac{2}{5} \cdot \zeta\left(\frac{5}{2}\right) \cdot \frac{x^{\frac{5}{2}}}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{5}{2}}}{\ln^2 x}\right),$$

where $\zeta(s)$ is the Riemann zeta-function, and $P(n)$ denotes the largest prime divisor of n .

Now we define a new arithmetical function $\bar{\Omega}(n)$ as follows: $\bar{\Omega}(1) = 0$; for $n > 1$, let $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_s^{\alpha_s}$ be the factorization of n into prime powers, then $\bar{\Omega}(n) = \alpha_1 p_1 + \alpha_2 p_2 + \dots + \alpha_s p_s$.

Obviously, for any positive integers m and n , we have $\bar{\Omega}(mn) = \bar{\Omega}(m) + \bar{\Omega}(n)$. That is, $\bar{\Omega}(n)$ is the additive function. The main purpose of this paper is using the elementary methods to study the mean value properties of $\bar{\Omega}(n)SL(n)$, and give a sharper asymptotic formula for it. That is, we shall prove the following conclusion:

Theorem. For any real number $x > 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \bar{\Omega}(n)SL(n) = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{d_i x^3}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^3}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),$$

where d_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, k$) are computable constants.

§2. Proof of the theorem

In this section, we shall use the elementary methods to complete the proof of the theorem.

In fact, for any positive integer $n > 1$, let $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_s^{\alpha_s}$ be the factorization of n into prime powers, then from [2] we know that

$$SL(n) = \max\{p_1^{\alpha_1}, p_2^{\alpha_2}, \dots, p_s^{\alpha_s}\}, \quad (1)$$

and we easily to know that

$$\bar{\Omega}(n) = \alpha_1 p_1 + \alpha_2 p_2 + \cdots + \alpha_s p_s. \quad (2)$$

Now we consider the summation

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \bar{\Omega}(n)SL(n). \quad (3)$$

We separate all integer n in the interval $[1, x]$ into four subsets A, B, C and D as follows:

A: $p \geq \sqrt{n}$ and $n = m \cdot p$;

B: $n^{\frac{1}{3}} < p_1 < p_2 \leq \sqrt{n}$ and $n = m \cdot p_1 \cdot p_2$, where p_i ($i = 1, 2$) are primes;

C: $n^{\frac{1}{3}} < p \leq \sqrt{n}$ and $n = m \cdot p^2$;

D: otherwise.

It is clear that if $n \in A$, then from (1) we know that $SL(n) = p$, and from (2) we know that $\bar{\Omega}(n) = \bar{\Omega}(m) + p$. Therefore, by the Abel's summation formula (See Theorem 4.2 of [6]) and the Prime Theorem (See Theorem 3.2 of [7]):

$$\pi(x) = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{a_i \cdot x}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),$$

where a_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, k$) are computable constants and $a_1 = 1$.

We have

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{n \in A} \bar{\Omega}(n)SL(n) &= \sum_{\substack{mp \leq x \\ m < p}} (\bar{\Omega}(m) + p)p = \sum_{\substack{mp \leq x \\ m < p}} p^2 + \sum_{\substack{mp \leq x \\ m < p}} (\bar{\Omega}(m)p) \\
&= \sum_{m \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{m < p \leq \frac{x}{m}} p^2 + O(x^2) \\
&= \sum_{m \leq \sqrt{x}} \left[\pi\left(\frac{x}{m}\right) \frac{x^2}{m^2} - \pi(m)m^2 - 2 \int_m^{\frac{x}{m}} \pi(t)tdt \right] + O(x^2) \\
&= \frac{1}{3}\zeta(3) \frac{x^3}{\ln x} + \sum_{i=2}^k \frac{b_i x^3}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^3}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right), \tag{4}
\end{aligned}$$

where $\zeta(s)$ is the Riemann zeta-function, and b_i ($i = 2, 3, \dots, k$) are computable constants.

Similarly, if $n \in B$, then we have $SL(n) = p_2$ and $\bar{\Omega}(n) = \bar{\Omega}(m) + p_1 + p_2$. So

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{n \in B} \bar{\Omega}(n)SL(n) &= \sum_{\substack{mp_1 p_2 \leq x \\ m < p_1 < p_2}} (\bar{\Omega}(m) + p_1 + p_2)p_2 = \sum_{\substack{mp_1 p_2 \leq x \\ m < p_1 < p_2}} p_2^2 + O\left(\sum_{\substack{mp_1 p_2 \leq x \\ m < p_1 < p_2}} p_1 p_2\right) \\
&= \sum_{m \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \sum_{m < p_1 \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{m}}} \sum_{p_1 < p_2 \leq \frac{x}{p_1 m}} p_2^2 + O(x^2) \\
&= \sum_{m \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \sum_{m < p_1 \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{m}}} \left[\pi\left(\frac{x}{p_1 m}\right) \frac{x^2}{p_1^2 m^2} - \pi(p_1)p_1^2 - 2 \int_{p_1}^{\frac{x}{p_1 m}} \pi(t)tdt \right] \\
&\quad + O(x^2) \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{c_i x^3}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^3}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right), \tag{5}
\end{aligned}$$

where c_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, k$) are computable constants.

Now we estimate the error terms in set C. Using the same method of proving (4), we have $SL(n) = p^2$ and $\bar{\Omega}(n) = \bar{\Omega}(m) + 2p$, so

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{n \in C} \bar{\Omega}(n)SL(n) &= \sum_{\substack{mp^2 \leq x \\ m < p}} (\bar{\Omega}(m) + 2p)p^2 = 2 \sum_{\substack{mp^2 \leq x \\ m < p}} p^3 + \sum_{\substack{mp^2 \leq x \\ m < p}} (\bar{\Omega}(m)p^2) \\
&= 2 \sum_{m \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \sum_{m < p \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{m}}} p^3 + O(x^{\frac{3}{2}}) \\
&= O(x^2). \tag{6}
\end{aligned}$$

Finally, we estimate the error terms in set D. For any integer $n \in D$, if $SL(n) = p$ then

$p \leq \sqrt{n}$; if $SL(n) = p^2$, then $p \leq n^{\frac{1}{3}}$; or $SL(n) = p^\alpha, \alpha \geq 3$. So we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \in D} \bar{\Omega}(n)SL(n) &\ll \sum_{\substack{mp \leq x \\ p \leq m}} (\bar{\Omega}(m) + p)p + \sum_{\substack{mp^2 \leq x \\ p \leq m}} (\bar{\Omega}(m) + 2p)p \\ &+ \sum_{\substack{mp^\alpha \leq x \\ p \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}, \alpha \geq 3}} (\bar{\Omega}(m)\alpha p)p^\alpha \ll \frac{x^2}{\ln x}. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Combining (4), (5), (6) and (7) we may immediately obtain the asymptotic formula

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \leq x} \bar{\Omega}(n)SL(n) &= \sum_{n \in A} \bar{\Omega}(n)SL(n) + \sum_{n \in B} \bar{\Omega}(n)SL(n) \\ &+ \sum_{n \in C} \bar{\Omega}(n)SL(n) + \sum_{n \in D} \bar{\Omega}(n)SL(n) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{d_i x^3}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^3}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right), \end{aligned}$$

where d_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, k$) are computable constants.

This completes the proof of Theorem.

References

- [1] F. Smarandache, Only Problems, not solutions, Chicago, Xiquan Publ. House, 1993.
- [2] A. Murthy, Some notions on least common multiples, Smarandache Notions Journal, **12**(2001), 307-309.
- [3] Le Maohua, An equation concerning the Smarandache LCM function, Smarandache Notions Journal, **14**(2004), 186-188.
- [4] Lv Zhongtian, On the F.Smarandache LCM function and its mean value, Scientia Magna, **3**(2007), No.1, 22-25.
- [5] Jianbin Chen, Value distribution of the F.Smarandache LCM function, Scientia Magna, **3**(2007), No.2, 15-18.
- [6] Tom M. Apostol, Introduction to Analytic Number Theory, New York, Springer-Verlag, 1976.
- [7] Pan Chengdong and Pan Chengbiao, The elementary proof of the prime theorem, Shanghai Science and Technology Press, Shanghai, 1988.
- [8] Xu Zhefeng, On the value distribution of Smarandache function, ACTA MATHEMATICA, Chinese Series, Sept., **49**(2006), No. 5, 961-1200.